

LEGAL PROCEDURE OF PROPERTY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article presents the legal status of the property of higher education organizations and issues of storage and management of this property. Legal frameworks regulating property rights in higher education institutions and the legal status of the legal nature of intellectual property have been researched.

Key words: financial management, financial stability, maintenance and increase of property, fixed asset turnover ratio, return on assets, student accommodation, administrative buildings, licensing agreements.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада олий таълим ташкилотларининг мол-мулкни ҳуқуқий ҳолати ва ушбу мол-мулкнинг сақлаш ва бошқариш масалалари келтирилган. Олий таълим муассасаларида мулк ҳуқуқларини тартибга солувчи ҳуқуқий асослар ва интеллектуал мулкнинг ҳуқуқий табиатининг ҳуқуқий ҳолати тадқиқ этилган.

Калит сўзлар: молиявий бошқарув, молиявий барқарорлик, мол-мулкни сақлаш ва кўпайтириш, асосий воситалар айланмаси коэффициенти, активлар рентабеллиги, талабалар турар жойлари, маъмурий бинолар, лицензиялаш шартномалари.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены правовое положение имущества организаций высшего образования и вопросы хранения и управления этим имуществом. Исследованы правовые основы, регулирующие права собственности в высших учебных заведениях, а также правовой статус правовой природы интеллектуальной собственности.

Ключевые слова: финансовый менеджмент, финансовая устойчивость, содержание и приумножение имущества, коэффициент оборачиваемости основных средств, рентабельность активов, студенческие общежития, административные здания, лицензионные договоры.

Asset maintenance in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan plays a critical role in ensuring the overall functionality and efficiency of the institution. Responsibility for asset maintenance often falls to facilities management teams, whose primary goal is to maintain the physical infrastructure of the institution through regular inspections, repairs, and upgrades. Effective maintenance strategies in higher education not only contribute to the safety and well-being of students and staff, but also help extend the life of property assets, resulting in long-term cost savings. The allocation of financial resources for asset maintenance should be carefully planned and prioritized to address the most critical and urgent needs first, and then regularly evaluated to identify emerging issues. By implementing strategic maintenance practices, higher education institutions in Uzbekistan can ensure a conducive learning and working environment for all stakeholders.

Asset utilization and optimization play a crucial role in the financial management of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan. Effective asset management allows these institutions to maximize their resources and improve their overall performance. By closely monitoring asset utilization indicators, such as inventory turnover ratio, fixed asset turnover ratio, and return on assets, which are calculated from economic categories, university administrators can identify areas for improvement and implement strategies to optimize asset utilization. This may include reallocating resources to increase efficiency and reduce waste, investing in new technologies, or streamlining operational processes. By effectively utilizing and optimizing assets, higher education institutions can achieve greater financial stability and sustainability, which in turn benefits their students, faculty, and stakeholders.

It is worth noting that tax legislation plays an important role in shaping the legal regime of property of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan. According to Article 243 of the current Tax Code, the sale of services in the field of education (training), including services for organizing tests and exams, in particular educational services in the field of primary, secondary, secondary specialized, technical and vocational, higher and postgraduate education, as well as services for providing additional education provided by educational institutions (organizations), as well as organizations that retrain and improve the skills of personnel, is exempt from turnover tax. [1]

The taxation of educational institutions can affect their financial sustainability and ability to fulfill their educational mission. In particular, the property tax privileges of higher education institutions are important in ensuring their

continued operation and development. However, the interpretation and application of tax legislation can vary, which can lead to potential difficulties for higher education institutions in managing a complex regulatory environment.

Understanding the characteristics of tax legislation affecting the property of higher education institutions is crucial for policymakers, administrators, and stakeholders to support the effective operation of educational institutions and ensure equal access to quality education. By studying the impact of tax laws on higher education property, one can gain insight into how to ensure a favorable regulatory environment for the development of educational institutions.

Budgeting for property-related expenses in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan is an important aspect that requires careful planning and foresight. Allocating funds for the preservation and expansion of property plays an important role in increasing the overall activity and competitiveness of these institutions. Proper budgeting creates a favorable environment for educational, scientific and administrative activities and ensures the adequate preservation of facilities. In addition, the need for periodic repairs, modernization and compliance with safety regulations should be taken into account when compiling a budget for property-related expenses. By forecasting and effectively distributing resources, higher education institutions can optimize the use of their property assets, ultimately increasing the reputation of the higher education institution and the quality of education provided. Therefore, a strategic and comprehensive approach to budgeting for property-related expenses is essential for the sustainable development and success of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan.

Ownership of research and innovation in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan is a complex and evolving issue. While the general principle is that researchers typically retain ownership of their work, institutions may have policies that grant them ownership of intellectual property created by their employees. This can lead to disputes over ownership and control of research results, especially where significant resources have been invested by the institution. Clear guidelines and agreements are essential to define the rights and obligations of all parties involved.

Licensing and commercialization of intellectual property are important aspects that higher education institutions in Uzbekistan need to consider. This process is directly regulated by the Civil Code. [2]

The process of licensing intellectual property allows these institutions to generate revenue by protecting and commercializing their inventions, research

results, and other innovative creations. By licensing their intellectual property, higher education institutions can collaborate with industry participants to bring these innovations to market, which is a win-win situation.

Commercialization of intellectual property can lead to the development of new products, services, and technologies, and stimulate economic growth and innovation in the region. At the same time, higher education institutions need to carefully examine the legal and regulatory framework governing intellectual property rights to ensure a fair distribution of rights and benefits. This requires clear policies and procedures for licensing agreements and commercialization strategies to maximize the impact of their intellectual assets.

When comparing the legal regime of property rights in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan with Western legal systems, one can observe significant contradictions. In Western legal systems, property rights are often focused on private property and the protection of private property. However, in Uzbekistan, the legal framework related to property ownership in higher education institutions is more complex, with a mixture of state and private property structures. This difference may stem from historical and cultural factors specific to each system. While Western legal systems may prioritize private property rights, the Uzbek system places greater emphasis on collective and state ownership structures in the higher education sector. Understanding these contrasting legal frameworks is crucial for scholars and policymakers seeking to streamline the complexity of property rights in higher education institutions.

Good international practices in the legal framework regulating property rights in higher education institutions provide valuable lessons for Uzbek universities. Uzbekistan could adopt a strategy to strengthen its legal order by studying successful models from countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and Germany, where property rights in academic institutions are clearly defined and protected. For example, implementing clear guidelines on ownership of intellectual property created by faculty and students could enhance innovation and research excellence.

In addition, establishing transparent decision-making mechanisms for property transactions in universities can prevent conflicts and ensure accountability. By incorporating these best practices, Uzbek higher education institutions can strengthen their governance structures and create a more conducive environment for scientific and scholarly development. Uzbek universities need

to learn from global experience to adapt to the evolving higher education governance environment.

The impact on higher education in Uzbekistan is broad and multifaceted, and the legal regime governing higher education institutions within the country is affected. The legal framework surrounding property rights in Uzbek higher education institutions not only affects institutional autonomy, but also plays a crucial role in shaping the overall quality and governance of these institutions. Since higher education institutions rely on property for a variety of purposes, such as research facilities, student housing, and administrative buildings, any uncertainty or lack of clarity in property rights can hinder the effectiveness of these institutions.

One of the unique challenges in higher education is the increasing demand for universities to balance academic freedom with the demands of society. While higher education institutions strive to uphold the principles of freedom of inquiry and expression, they are also facing increasing pressures to address social issues, promote diversity, and respond to the political climate. This tension can lead to conflicts within the academic community and difficulties in maintaining a neutral, impartial learning environment. In addition, the rise of online learning platforms and the rapid pace of technological development are creating another obstacle for higher education institutions to remain relevant and competitive in the global marketplace. As universities navigate these complexities, they must adapt their traditional structures and methods to meet the changing needs of students and the demands of a rapidly changing world.

Despite the complexity of the legal regime of property rights in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, the main findings of this study highlight several important aspects. Firstly, it was found that the property rights of these higher education institutions are tightly regulated by a complex network of laws and regulations. These regulations cover the ownership and management of assets, including land, buildings, and intellectual property. Secondly, the study highlighted the challenges that higher education institutions face in preserving and expanding their property resources due to bureaucratic obstacles and legal restrictions. Finally, the study highlighted the need to reform the legal framework governing property rights in higher education institutions to ensure transparency, efficiency, and fair treatment for all stakeholders. Taken together, this study contributes to a better understanding of the complex legal nature of property rights in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan.

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